

Scrotal steatocystomas: A Rare Presentation

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Scrotal steatocystomas present as multiple sebum-filled cysts confined to the scrotum, in this case in a young adult male. They are usually part of steatocystoma multiplex, a rare autosomal-dominant disorder linked to keratin-17 mutations. Lesions are typically painless, yet patients seek treatment for sitting discomfort, cosmetic worries (often before marriage) or episodes of infection or inflammation. Management options include staged excision, laser ablation and electrocautery.

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